

Food systems that support
transitions to hEalthy And
Sustainable dieTs

OUTCOMES AND INSIGHTS FROM CO-DESIGN WORKSHOPS IN FEAST LIVING LABS

FEAST 3.3. Community involvement

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BACKGROUND

One of the main goals of the FEAST project is to co-create innovative and effective tools, programs and strategies with key stakeholders in Europe that support consumers in adopting healthy and sustainable diets and lifestyles. To reach this objective, it is important that we actively involve the communities for which we develop these solutions. Working with living labs is one of the core elements of the Feast program because they promote co-creation while leveraging the participation of end-users (citizens, including vulnerable groups) by gathering their real-world insights and local knowledge. To support this work, we created a guideline to conduct workshops in which living labs can co-design solutions to address food-related challenges in their communities that help (vulnerable) citizen groups to make healthier and more sustainable food choices.

Co-design methods have their roots in participatory designs and are a promising approach for engaging citizens and stakeholders in intervention and policy-making processes. It empowers participants to express their understanding and needs concerning an issue and creates opportunities to generate new perspectives, shared insights, and attitudinal or behavioural change. The stakeholders involved in this co-design process can be multiple: it is possible that the participants are the target group of the solution, but they can also be relevant stakeholders that play an essential role in shaping the diets of the target group (e.g. if the vulnerable group are children, this can be parents, teachers, school boards, etc.). Co-design workshops have proven to be an effective methodology in identifying the needs of a community and co-creating (policy-based) solutions and interventions (Bason, 2016²; Kim & Nam, 2022³; Kimbell, 2017⁴).

This document can be used as addendum or inspirational guide to the co-design workshop handbook (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15730598>). The handbook is developed to guide facilitators through the process of organizing a co-creation workshop. This report compiles and analyzes the outcomes of several workshops conducted across four different living labs within the FEAST project, offering valuable **insights and inspiration for other living labs**.

Living labs interested in running a co-design workshop can use this structured process to foster healthy, sustainable eating within their communities. FEAST provides resources, including facilitator guidelines, templates, and tools, ensuring that the workshop is easy to implement. For more information, see the handbook of the workshop as well as the reflections on applying the method in this report.

² Bason, C. 2016. Design for Policy. Abingdon: Routledge.

³ Kim, C., & Nam, K. Y. (2022). Policy Puzzle Game: Making policy ideas feasible and acceptable in policy co-design. *CoDesign*, 18(4), 448–465. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15710882.2021.1995440>

⁴ Kimbell, L. (2017). Design in the Time of Policy Problems. *Annual Review of Policy Design*, 5(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.21606/drs.2016.498>

WORKSHOP

Community workshop to co-design solutions for better access to healthy sustainable food

Workshop overview:

The workshop enables participants to collaboratively identify barriers to healthy and sustainable eating and design solutions that cater to their specific community needs and qualities. It is based on participatory methods, emphasizing the co-creation of interventions that encourage better dietary behaviour.

Key components in three rounds:

- **Graph over time and dream:** Participants visualize how food-related challenges have evolved in their community and envision future scenarios.
- **Mapping barriers and qualities:** Using a cognitive mapping approach, participants collaboratively identify barriers to healthy food consumption and existing strengths within the community.
- **Solution pathways:** Groups brainstorm and develop potential interventions, make the connection with the bottlenecks and qualities and identify key stakeholders for implementation.

Outcomes and benefits for living labs:

- **Identify challenges and opportunities:** Through structured exercises, participants map bottlenecks and qualities that might be supportive in solving the problem and focus on points for improvement.
- **Tailored approach:** In the workshop the participants create common understanding of the challenge the living lab is facing. The workshop can be adapted to focus on specific community needs, such as child nutrition or local food environments.
- **Co-create solutions:** The workshop encourages participants to design practical solutions that are feasible and impactful for the community.

- **Actionable outcomes:** The solutions are connected with the bottlenecks and qualities. The solutions generated have a strong support base, with a focus on interventions that can be implemented within the community. The workshop facilitates a holistic approach to food systems. The level of responsibility (micro, meso or macro) is clear.
- **Empower local people:** The workshop can involve only citizens, but can also include a mix of inhabitants (including vulnerable groups) and key stakeholders (e.g., policymakers, school officials) or solely stakeholders. It fosters cooperation among diverse groups, ensuring that all voices are heard.

OUTCOMES

Three living labs from the FEAST consortium were interested to conduct the workshop in their community to co-create solutions which support their citizens in making healthier and more sustainable food choices. The **participating living labs** were Oxfordshire, Ghent and Tuscany. After developing the workshop we first **piloted** the setup in a living lab in Leuven to test whether the design delivered on the intended outcomes and could be optimized where needed. The participants in Leuven were not directly linked to the FEAST living labs, but also interested in developing solutions to a specific food challenge in their neighbourhood.

For both Leuven and Oxfordshire workshops were conducted with relevant stakeholders from the vulnerable groups. In Ghent and Tuscany participants were professional stakeholders providing opportunities for citizens to develop healthier and more sustainable food choices.

A

LEUVEN

Pilot of the workshop. The pilot was not conducted with participants of the FEAST living lab in Leuven. However, the participants were recruited through the network of FEAST partners in Leuven, specifically through schools as healthy food for young children is a challenge in the city. The main objective of the workshop in Leuven was centred around supporting **healthy food choices for young children**, for example through nutrition in schools. Participants were moms with children in primary school age.

The workshop's target audience was **mothers with children of primary school age**

1. Graph over time and dream

In the timeline exercise – **graph over time** - participants reflected on the evolution of healthy and sustainable eating behaviours. They discussed the eating behaviour and food environment over the past and shared their perspectives on how the consumption of healthy and sustainable foods might develop in the future.

Healthy and sustainable eating

Prevalence
of the
challenge

- "Two-sided: many people have started eating better, but the availability of unhealthy food has increased significantly.
- Marketing around unhealthy food has grown enormously.
- The differences have become greater. The common ground is not like it used to be.
- The options were much more limited in the past.
- Now there is a very wide range, but with more extremes.
- Food is everywhere nowadays, so children are constantly exposed to it.
- Affordability: people buy according to their budget, and healthy options are often too expensive."

Their **dream** is:

Elements of the dream were:

- "That I can serve something that everyone enjoys eating. Not just children's meals.
- How do you get children familiar with unfamiliar flavours (anti-traditional Flemish food)?
- Only eating meat once a week (everywhere).
- The principle of finishing your plate = good, and not finishing = bad - is a bizarre parenting rule.
- We need less old-fashioned views regarding portion sizes.
- Tasty, healthy food for everyone + it should be fun.

- Eating = a cosy, social moment, offering a different way of eating.
- More knowledge needed among people about sustainable, healthy food.
- Schools should do more to educate about food: third grade and up."

2. Bottlenecks and qualities

In the first round, participants identified existing bottlenecks by writing them on post-its, which they then placed on a poster displayed on the wall. The poster included three dimensions—micro, meso, and macro levels—but did not yet categorize the bottlenecks in terms of 'food literacy,' 'food preferences,' 'food availability,' or 'food affordability.' These categories were later mapped by the researchers.

Most of the bottlenecks experienced by participants were at the meso level, specifically within their immediate food environment (Figure 1). They noted the low availability of healthy and sustainable food options in supermarkets, take-away outlets, and schools, combined with the high availability and promotion of fast food. The lack of sales restrictions and the high cost of healthier alternatives were also mentioned as bottlenecks.

Despite these challenges, participants also recognized several positive developments at the meso level, particularly in the school (Figure 2). Warm meals are available, unhealthy snacks as treatments have been phased out, and there is increased availability of vegan and vegetarian options in the community. Additionally, there is more focus on providing smaller portions and healthier options tailored to children. Several initiatives are contributing to the availability of healthier and more sustainable food, setting positive examples for the community.

Figure 1 - Bottlenecks mapped in Living Lab Leuven

Figure 2 - Qualities mapped in Living Lab Leuven

3. Solutions pathway

To the question, "Which solutions would be most effective and efficient to implement now?" the following answers were given (also see Figure 3):

- An app to spread knowledge
- Nutrition education as a regular subject in schools: one hour a week for everyone, especially in secondary schools

Other option that were mentioned:

- Providing school meals/ lunch/ snacks/ fruit
- Restrictive regulations (marketing, advertising, sweets at the checkout)
- Free water for the children
- Eco-cheques

Figure 3 -Solutions mapped in living lab Leuven

Additional ideas from the group, involving television, were:

1. An interactive TV show with audience interaction on the topic of healthy eating (Karolien Olaerts, Sara Renson, Loïc Kok has a cooking show on TV)
2. Interaction between the studio audience and viewers at home: workshop
3. Integrate nutrition into the TV show "Helden"
4. Find ambassadors for healthy eating: Famous Flemish people?
5. An experimental show where you offer children certain food choices and observe which surrounding factors influence their decisions (similar to British programs that analyze social relationships in classroom settings, particularly in preschool classes)

B

OXFORDSHIRE

The living lab in Oxfordshire is working with six community groups, to examine the barriers that make it difficult for parents with children under 5 and older adults 65+ to adopt healthier and more sustainable eating habits, and to identify and implement innovative strategies that enable these groups to integrate healthier and more sustainable food choices into their daily lives.

Their intervention is exploring both community cooking interventions and a digital hub of healthy family friendly recipes, evidence based nutritional advice and meal plans.

The target group for this workshop **was parents with children under 5**. The workshop is conducted in five (small) groups, with parents (circa 35 persons in total).

1. Graph over time and dream

The mentioned **dreams** were:

- Being able to grow food in a garden (at school or in an own garden - space and skills/knowledge) (9x)
- Time/ resources/ inspiration to cook from scratch (4x)
- Access to better quality fruit and vegetables/ foods (in shops) (4x)
- Minimise food waste (3x)
- Affordable healthy food, access to loose fresh fruit and veg/ healthier low-cost options available (3x)
- Access to more locally grown/ organic food (2x)
- Conscious buying, knowledge and understanding of what to buy in season (1x)
- Everyone in my household eating the same meal (1x)
- Affordable seeds and growing equipment for gardening (1x)
- Access to a wide variety of food in one place / shop (1x)
- Less temptation of unhealthy foods in shops (1x)
- Talking/ educating around food (1x)

- Ability for more sharing meals and resources (with neighbours / community) (1x)
- Better advertising of fresh fruit and veg and less junk food / fast foods (1x)

2. Bottlenecks and qualities

Similar as in Leuven, participants identified existing bottlenecks in the first round by writing them on post-its, which they then placed on a poster displayed on the wall. The poster included three dimensions—micro, meso, and macro levels—but did not yet categorize the bottlenecks in terms of 'food literacy,' 'food preferences,' 'food availability,' or 'food affordability.' These categories were later mapped by the researchers.

Many of the bottlenecks participants encountered were at the micro level, particularly regarding their partners' and children's food preferences, as well as the convenience and quick availability of fast food (Figure 4). Participants also reported limited access to seasonal and local foods, a lack of variety in food shops, and insufficient space for growing their own food. Additionally, low levels of knowledge and skills related to healthy and sustainable eating, combined with high food prices, were identified as key barriers.

Participants highlighted as qualities that many are already actively engaged in reducing food waste, minimizing plastic use, and modelling positive behaviours for their children (Figure 5).

Figure 4 - Bottlenecks mapped in living lab Oxfordshire

Figure 5 - Qualities mapped in living lab Oxfordshire

3. Solutions pathway

To the question, "Which solutions would be most effective and efficient to implement now?" the most frequent answers were (also see Figure 6):

- A free app/ platform/ website with knowledge/ recipes/ meal plans (toddler/ family friendly, with ways to involve kids) (12x)
- A free community growing/ help yourself garden/ family allotment (8x)
- Cooking classes, using seasonal veg and tips for reducing waste (8x)
- Clearer communication on larder/ community fridge/ free or cheap services are available to help residents (5x)

Figure 6 - Solutions mapped in living lab Oxfordshire

Other option that were mentioned:

- More veg boxes or cheaper boxes (for almost out of date produce in shops and supermarkets) (2x)
- Information/ a source/ classes on good growing, what to grow when (2x)
- Food education at primary schools (with better use of teachers and peers' influence/ visit farms) (2x)
- Availability of pre-peeled and pre-chopped (affordable) veg (1x)
- Affordable healthy foods, deals or offering some local-specific promotions (1x)
- More support from shops to understand how to cook (1x)
- Variety of cheaper supermarkets close by (1x)
- Free transport to local supermarkets – shuttle bus service (1x)
- Provide a cheaper, healthier alternative to takeaways, e.g. a new healthy café (1x)
- Promote family fruit and veg vouchers and discounts (1x)
- More opportunities for growing at home (3x)
- More opportunities for kids to volunteer in gardening (1x)
- Farmer market/ shop at market for one treat, so that you are still supporting producers (3x)
- Connect farmers with local communities, via food sharing (1x)
- Summer or Harvest festival fair / event (1x)
- Seed swop locally (1x)
- Campaign to showcase healthy and balanced meal ideas using local produce (1x)
- Map of local foraging spots (fruit trees, blackberries) for community use (1x)
- Access to resources on reducing waste (1x)
- Information and knowledge sharing about best before dates / use by dates (1x)
- Blog/newsletter sharing information about seasonal produce and where to buy it locally (1x)
- Recipe cards available for free in community spaces (1x)
- Food-sharing library with recipe books (1x)
- Food/cooking provisions for teenagers; opportunities for older teens to get involved in cooking and growing food (1x)
- Fun and interactive food activities (1x)
- Baby weaning class – where babies get to taste and feel different foods (1x)
- Playgroups focused on healthy eating and access to children's garden (1x)
- Posters promoting healthy alternatives to junk food (e.g., healthier chicken nuggets) (1x)

C

GHENT

Ghent has been a pioneer in the field of sustainable food and sustainable food policy for years. In 2013, the City launched the Ghent and Garde food strategy in collaboration with many stakeholders. Shortly afterwards, the Food Council was established, the participatory policy body of Ghent and Garde. In the years that followed, the food policy was further shaped and Ghent determined three strategic objectives which are used as a framework to determine Ghent's food policy and to evaluate results:

- a short and sustainable food chain
- everyone eats sustainable
- nothing is wasted

The City of Ghent was one of the first cities to develop a local food policy. In 2020, they assessed the food environments in the Water sports and Heilig Hart neighborhoods. The Heilig Hartwijk was then defined as a food swamp (lots of junkfood offer), the Water sportswijk as a food desert (hardly any food offer).

The main objective of the living lab in Ghent is to improve access to healthy and sustainable food for individuals in vulnerable situations. A survey among users of various food initiatives showed that people in poverty have little or no knowledge of the supply of healthy and sustainable food in the neighbourhood. For various food suppliers who are active in the neighbourhood, it also appeared that they themselves know little to nothing about the offer of another supplier. The aim of this workshop is therefore to get to know each other and to come up with new actions whereby **the target group finds its way to the various initiatives.**

The **participants** in the workshop are all professionally or voluntarily active in food supply for consumers in the neighbourhood. Their background differentiated from a social restaurant where customers eat at differentiated (lower) rates, non-profit organizations of professionals and volunteers which collect and redistribute food surpluses or prepared meals, support people in poverty in various areas of life, community (street) workers, health promoters or district directors who know what is urgent in a neighbourhood, and find solutions to improve the quality of life of people in poverty and connect with city policy, district health centres with dieticians, physiotherapists and nurses collaborating or an organisation uniting farmers and organising weekly markets.

1. Graph over time and dream

For the **dream** the group discussed what the different participating organisations see for their future, but also came up with a joint dream:

Elements of the individual dreams were (also see Figure 7):

- A shared herb garden
- Workshops on preserving techniques and harvest surpluses
- Urban agriculture for people who use the food support
- Tasty half-half meals for customers
- New locations for food waste redistribution and central kitchen
- Scaling up the cooking team: finding new customers
- Consolidate collaborations

Figure 7 -Timeline with dreams in living lab Lab Ghent (in Dutch)

2. Solutions pathway

As participants enjoyed to get to know the other organizations and were very impressed to hear each others effort to reach their dream in providing opportunities for all to eat a fair price, the facilitators chose to combine the discussion on opportunities and bottlenecks in the next exercise.

Underlying bottlenecks and qualities

- Fairness for all, sell at a reasonable price, but also being compensated for possible loss.
- No need for referrals, good food should be as accessible as possible for all in need.
- Hartetroef has facilities, but no opportunities to differentiate in pricing. Also an ID is needed to be able to pay a lower price and not all visitors have an ID. And the difference between the lowest and highest price level is too large, consumers with low incomes who not meet the criteria, for example because they don't live in Ghent, can't afford to pay 20€ for a daily special.

Solutions

Opportunities were discussed based on the bottlenecks and qualities and per dream defined. All categorized at micro, meso and macro level.

1. Everyone eats for a fair price.

Micro

- a) Share concrete information on a flyer: prices of the products on the market, prices of the daily specials.
- b) Apply Enchanté to the market? "Delayed steak, butter, celeriac": pay for an extra meal for another consumer when you buy one for yourself.

Meso

- a) Evening experience in Hartetroef where there is no fixed social rate, but a free contribution or solidarity rate -> Discussion with the city of Ghent about the "grey zone" solidarity rates.
- b) Investigate how a solidarity rate can work on a market or restaurant: e.g. a marble system on a market (somewhere in the south of France) -> Discussion with customers (e.g. farmers market): what is their opinion on solidarity rates.
- c) More preserving and fermenting of surplus vegetables from LSF, market -> Workshops on preserving and in different languages, by and with different communities (Turkish & Bulgarian).

Macro

- a) City of Ghent: Reviewing social rates in social restaurants: what about the grey zone? Are there opportunities that just slip through the net?
- b) Local land for local sales market.
- c) More CSA farms on clean land.
- d) More ownership.

2. We are a community in which food connects us

Micro

- a) Make the offer of each provider known by creating a calendar (per week / month), district food guide (where can who go?) -> City can facilitate e.g. Google Maps at district level.
- b) Board / living wall in the church with photos of people and food from the district. Work very visually, residents are co-owners, hang things up themselves. Must be a kind of photo of the district "meeting and food".

Meso

- a) (Getting to) know each other. Who what when how: for referrers and for people themselves.
- b) Developing 2 instruments? there used to be padlet, but it is no longer used. It should not be an extra app, but something directly usable.
- c) Sit together with the food providers at regular times. Can also be between pot and pit and does not have to be a real meeting.
- d) Use the church space for meeting.

Macro:

- a) City of Ghent: Facilitate and support in: space, storage, financial support, thinking about other possibilities and referral.

3. Other actions

- a) Create a communication platform for referrers: Map, calendar, food guide (or something else that works for everyone). City of Ghent will work out a concrete proposal and test it with everyone.
- b) Social rates / grey zone / evening activities in the church: City of Ghent will test the possibilities with local social policy and local social economy.
- c) Solidarity rates on the market: Find other examples (France) and see what is usable.

D

TUSCANY

National documents and several researches indicate that the Italian population often exhibits unhealthy dietary behaviours that do not align with the mediterranean diet, leading to an increased risk of overweight, obesity, the development of chronic noncommunicable diseases (NCD) and eating disorders. Moreover, from a social perspective, negative consequences on the quality of life and high pressure on the health and social system can be found. In order to tackle this issue, findings emphasize how crucial it is to develop *life-course* interventions that can change and improve food habits and choices towards a healthy approach, especially considering and mitigating the barriers that may hinder this change. Tuscany living lab Lab aims to promote a healthy and conscious approach towards food and nutrition in middle and high school students, their families and the elderly attending senior centres.

The specific challenge for this workshop was on how to sustainably continue the developed solution of interventions by nutritionists after the FEAST project.

Purpose: how to structure outpatient pediatric nutrition clinic

Participants: Director of Piana di Lucca District Zone, Coordinator of the Lucca Primary Care Unit, Administrative contact person for the Piana di Lucca District Zone, Tuscany LL Nutritionist

Facilitator: Tuscany LL Psychologist

To introduce the workshop and participants, the facilitators developed a quiz in which both fun facts about food and more “serious” questions were included to introduce some important issues to take into account such as the epidemic spread of overweight and obesity, health costs, and the associated stigma that has implications for both psychological and social well-being. For some questions such as stigma an image (example below) was used to ask participants to structure their thoughts around the topic.

To further introduce the topic, which was helpful because of the different backgrounds of the professionals involved, a poster was created to highlight the main points about overweight and obesity and the usefulness of supporting initiatives that can counter and manage the phenomenon. Specific attention was given to:

- results of national surveillance on the Tuscan territory concerning overweight and obesity
- social, psychological, health and economic impact
- actions and strategies undertaken at the European and National level to counter the phenomenon of overweight and obesity
- presentation of the pediatric nutrition outpatient clinic as a concrete “answer” to the emerged needs
- description of the characteristics of the outpatient clinic

Photo of the (handmade) poster board used:

1. Graph over time and dream

The idea to conduct the workshop in living lab Tuscany was created from the wish to sustain the presence and work of the dieticians within the community after the end of project FEAST. This was set as dream for the session. The workshop time was used to further look into bottlenecks and qualities and develop solutions.

2. Bottlenecks and qualities

For the group it was fruitful to think of bottlenecks in their current work with patients, however it was found too complex to identify the respective level: micro, meso or macro.

The following bottlenecks were identified by the group of professionals:

- a) Excessive bureaucracy.
- b) Lack of sufficient communication from the outpatient pediatric nutrition clinic.
- c) Lack of a psychologist to work alongside the nutritionist (management of a potential drop out).
- d) Lack of citizen culture on the issue.
- e) Lack of widespread Authority's culture on the importance of the issue.
- f) Lack of a broader Authority's culture on the topic of prevention (only screening system is structured).
- g) Lack of personnel.
- h) Lack of financial resources and specific funds.
- i) Nature of pilot projects: difficult to extend without sustained monitoring.

For the qualities, the following elements were identified:

- a) Presence of the North West Local Health Authority's ranking list (biologists) for outpatient specialty care.
- b) District motivation to structure the outpatient pediatric nutrition clinic.
- c) Possibility to involve other Units (e.g., pediatrics, eating disorders unit, diabetes, sports medicine, psychology).
- d) Existence of the Authority Nutrition Surveillance Board.
- e) Good demand from citizens.
- f) Existence of health plans such as the National Chronic Disease Plan (obesity recognized as a chronic disease) and the Guidelines for Preventing and Combating Overweight and Obesity.
- g) Presence of communication office to increase communication.

3. Solutions pathway

The following useful actions were identified:

- a) Strengthening the communication line through: writing articles, organizing local events and publicizing the service through social channels, newspapers and TV (connection with communication office).
- b) Creating a communication channel with the Region to identify the presence of Region wide actions/goals in line with the outpatient clinic.
- c) Delineating a Strategic Plan Project with the appropriate Authority's Units. Consequently, presenting the project to the Units of interest and creating a working group to collaborate on the drafting of the project.
- d) Involving a Regional contact person in the working group and project drafting.
- e) Improving the management of follow-up: request to manage the scheduling of follow-up appointments directly from the specialist.
- f) Connecting the outpatient clinic to a screening program and including this proposal within the project.
- g) Including the topic of counteracting physical inactivity for greater sustainability of the project: involving sports associations and municipal bodies since the motivations for inactivity are also social → transformation of the outpatient clinic into a social-health service.
- h) Preparing a request to the Authority Management to present the service.

The group used a poster board to report the post-its with the solutions and then linked the post-its for bottlenecks and qualities. Then for each solution, the main actors for execution and timelines were given.

Connection between Main Actions-Stakeholder-Timeline

A. Strengthening the communication line through: writing articles, organizing local events and publicizing the service through social channels, newspapers and TV (connection with communication office)

- Main stakeholder: contact person within the communication office
- Timeline: once the structuring process has begun
- Qualities that facilitate this action: Presence of communication office to increase communication
- Barriers that are mitigated/reduced through this action: Lack of sufficient communication from the outpatient pediatric nutrition clinic, Lack of citizen culture on the issue, Lack of widespread Authority's culture on the importance of the issue

B. Creating a communication channel with the Region to identify the presence of Regional wide actions/goals in line with the outpatient clinic.

D. Involving a Regional contact person in the working group and project drafting.

- Main stakeholder: contact person within the regional department of prevention
- Timeline: immediately, first thing to do
- Qualities that facilitate this action: Existence of the Authority Nutrition Surveillance Board, Existence of health plans such as the National Chronic Disease Plan (obesity recognized as a chronic disease) and the Guidelines for Preventing and Combating Overweight and Obesity, Good demand from citizen
- Barriers that are mitigated/reduced through this action: Lack of financial resources and specific funds

C. Delineating a Strategic Plan Project with the appropriate Authority's Units. Consequently, presenting the project to the Units of interest and creating a working group to collaborate on the drafting of the project.

F. Connecting the outpatient clinic to a screening program and including this proposal within the project

G. Including the topic of counteracting physical inactivity for greater sustainability of the project: involving sports associations and municipal bodies since the motivations for inactivity are also social transformation of the outpatient clinic into a social-health service

- Main stakeholder: contact persons/coordinators of the Authority's Units.
- Timeline: after the contact with the regional part
- Qualities that facilitate this action: Possibility to involve other Units (e.g., pediatrics, eating disorders unit, diabetes, sports medicine, psychology)
- Barriers that are mitigated/reduced through this action: Lack of a psychologist to work alongside the nutritionist (management of a potential drop out), Lack of widespread

Authority's culture on the importance of the issue, Lack of a broader Authority's culture on the topic of prevention (only screening system is structured), Lack of personnel

E. Improving the management of follow-up: request to manage the scheduling of follow-up appointments directly from the specialist

- Main stakeholder: contact person within the administrative service
- Timeline: possibility to send an email with the request immediately
- Qualities that facilitate this action: Good demand from Citizen
- Barriers that are mitigated/reduced through this action: Excessive bureaucracy

H. Preparing a request to the Authority Management to present the service

- Main stakeholder: Authority Management
- Timeline: as a last thing, but by the end of March
- Qualities that facilitate this action: Presence of the North West Local Health Authority's ranking list (biologists) for outpatient specialty care
- Barriers that are mitigated/reduced through this action: Nature of pilot projects: difficult to extend without sustained monitoring

“District motivation to structure the outpatient pediatric nutrition clinic” is a quality that cuts across all actions

CONCLUSIONS AND REFLECTIONS

1. General conclusions and outcomes

This workshop is developed to support the FEAST living labs in co creating solutions for healthier and more sustainable food choices (with vulnerable groups) within their communities. In this final chapter of this report we reflect on both the outcomes of the workshops in relation to the existing literature on drivers and barriers to healthy and sustainable food choices as well as the design and usability of the workshop.

We noticed that most participants in the conducted workshops really enjoyed the discussions and activities in the workshops. The design allowed them to explore what changes would be needed in their community to make the transition to healthier and sustainable food choices from a fresh and different perspective. Through co creating within a group with different backgrounds they came up with new solutions to work on the challenge their community is facing. Due to available time, the solutions could not be really thought through well enough for participants to also develop an action plan and leave with concrete ideas for follow up.

In the handbook it's mentioned that the group of participants could also be a mix of citizens combined with professional stakeholders in the environment of the vulnerable groups who could also have a role in acting on the developed solutions. When discussing the set up with the different FEAST living labs, the design seemed also interesting to run these sessions solely with professional stakeholders. When looking into the outcomes we noticed that the design works well, also these stakeholders were really inspired by the outcomes of their workshop, however the outcomes itself are on a different level and not comparable with the insights from working with the (vulnerable) citizens themselves. Although this might be related to the content and challenge of the two professional stakeholder workshops, outcomes and insights seem to be more related to processes on working together than on actual outcomes on healthier and more sustainable food choices. For the comparison of the outcomes with the literature on drivers and barriers to healthy and sustainable food choices in the next paragraph we focused solely on the outcomes of the workshops in Leuven and Oxfordshire. We did notice that, for the professional stakeholders, it was easier to come to concrete solutions an action plans, possible because these are closer to their sphere of influence compared to the citizens, which stimulates ownership for the solutions.

Reflections on similarities and differences on the outcomes compared to existing literature

Based on the comparison between the scientific literature on drivers and barriers for healthy and sustainable food choices and the findings from the living labs in Leuven and Oxfordshire, focusing on mothers with young children, a few general remarks could be made regarding similarities and differences (see annex for more details):

- Bottlenecks relate to accessibility and affordability: a significant barrier identified in both the literature and the living labs is the cost and availability of healthy and sustainable foods. High prices and limited access to fresh and sustainable options often deter people, especially families with young children, from adopting healthier diets.
- Influence of time and convenience: time constraints are a major barrier, mentioned both in the literature and the living labs. For mothers, the need for convenience due to busy family schedules makes it challenging to choose healthy, sustainable foods that often require more preparation time. Especially in combination with children with limited preferences.
- Lack of skills and knowledge: lack of skills and knowledge about healthy and sustainable options make it harder to consistently choose healthier diets. This was identified as really important barriers from the literature and also from the mothers within the living labs.
- Social influence and peer pressure: The literature suggests that social norms and the peers play a significant role in food choices. Mothers in Leuven nor Oxfordshire did mentioned this, probably because the children are of young age and more influenced by the partners then from their peers. This will shift when they grow older.

Differences between the two living labs (Leuven vs. Oxfordshire):

- Health versus sustainability: In Oxfordshire the qualities mentioned were more described in terms of sustainability, especially in the reduction of food waste, whereas in Leuven the focus was more on healthy diets. This might have been related to the specific challenge and dream.
- Local food environment: The living labs in Leuven and Oxfordshire revealed some differences in the local food environment. In Leuven, there was a stronger emphasis on the availability of local, sustainable products and the community's role in promoting these options. There was also more focus on the school environment. In contrast, in Oxfordshire, mothers highlighted more challenges in finding affordable, sustainable options in their local supermarkets. Also was the focus more on the level of the household and less on the food environment.
- Community support and initiatives: In Leuven, mothers mentioned the importance of local initiatives and community support systems (e.g., farmers' markets, food cooperatives) that made it easier for them to access sustainable food. Oxfordshire mothers, on the other hand, emphasized the lack of community-driven initiatives and the lack of access of local food and space.

Conclusion:

Overall, the living lab findings align with the scientific literature on key drivers and barriers for healthy and sustainable food choices, such as affordability, accessibility, knowledge, skills, convenience and time. However, there are noticeable differences in the adjustments in schools, local food environments and community support structures between Leuven and Oxfordshire, which influence how mothers perceive the qualities and barriers. These local variations show the importance of co-designing interventions together with the community and connect to what is seen as quality of the community and their inhabitants.

2. General reflections on the workshop design and co creating with vulnerable groups

In general the set-up of the workshop was well evaluated and lead to interesting results. Based on some general and more specific reflections we observed that for the set-up of the workshop it's worthwhile to take into account opportunities and limitations of the group to accommodate to their needs. So depending on for example the level of knowledge, time available, type of participants or to what extent the group is familiar with each other, the workshop set up can slightly be adapted with the examples below.

General comments on conducting the workshop:

- Group size: Small group sizes could have made it more difficult to generate a lot of ideas and discussions but also made it intimate and personal, because people felt free to share. In too large groups participants can also lose focus.
- Duration of the workshop: the full workshop was a lot to get through in the time allowed. "You need the right balance between getting through content at the right pace and the requirements of group." "I noticed some participants experiencing a certain fatigue and that point, certain people clearly took the lead." It's important to ensure that everyone stays involved, as otherwise some input might be missed due to participation fatigue. Moderators should allow for time and space for participants to contribute to each question which is difficult if there's not enough time.
- Time per exercise: It would be good to schedule more time for the solutions and if needed action planning. To be able to get specific on these solutions and the detail of what they would look like. There was not always enough time left at the end of the workshop. To be able to go more into detail on the action plans it might be worthwhile to schedule a second workshop, depending on the need for concrete outcomes by the living lab.
- Complexity: Moderators working with citizens mentioned that a lot of complex concepts were introduced during the workshop, which were for some participants difficult to provide input to on the spot. Perhaps some information could be provided before the workshop to set expectations. And perhaps the assignment could be clarified a bit more, whereby carefully considering which words to use.

- Materials: Large models to display help in interaction within the group and there should also be enough solutions/ideas and stakeholder cards to build the solutions pathway. Specifically for the consent form it's important that it's in the mother language of the participants.

Comments on elements of the workshop:

- The 'icebreaker' was greatly appreciated by the participants because it triggered a relaxed atmosphere among the participants and provided a 'light' introduction to the topic.
- Formulating one specific dream was difficult for the groups. The risk is that the facilitator's role becomes too directive, when they try to enforce this. Maybe someone from the group can take the role of note-taker to support group consensus. When summarizing the outcomes, the group can refer back to this (since not everyone remembers everything that was said).
- Drawing the graph over time: was found to be too abstract and the questions (such as what is the problem, what is the prevalence) were not equally clear to the participants.
- The discussion on bottlenecks was evaluated very fruitful and interactive. However, for some participants it was difficult to identify the layer (macro, meso, micro) in which to place the bottlenecks. Also because some aspects were experienced as shared between two layers or cascaded results of weaknesses in other layers.
- The discussion on qualities easily shifted to what people personally do (micro level) regarding 'good practices' and aspects on meso and macro levels were forgotten. It's important for the facilitator to keep this focus. Also there was a strong tendency not to stay focused on the strengths and anticipate to the solutions part.
- Formulating solutions: there was in most workshops too little time left for this part. To ensure enough time, in one workshop the exercise on qualities and bottlenecks was combined, in others they linked post its with solutions to the post-its for bottlenecks and qualities instead of the available bottlenecks and qualities cards. However, linking solutions to bottlenecks and qualities was experienced as a good exercise for 'thinking through'. If possible, and there is already sufficient knowledge of the barriers, facilitators can consider to partially fill in the models beforehand. During the workshop, the focus can then primarily be on what needs to be added or removed.

Specific reflections on implementing the workshop with citizens

For the group mothers with young children, it helped to relate the time span more to their personal lives. For example, how sustainable and healthy were your parents' eating habits? How does it look for you personally? Do you think our eating habits will naturally become healthier and more sustainable in the future without deliberate actions or awareness? And what will it look like for our children? Also, for them, it helped to rephrase the dream, with an emphasis on thinking about "your future and your kids future".

The moderators also reflected that in all of the workshops it was best to make it as informal and as relevant to the local context as possible. The target group often brought kids to the sessions and parents needed to look after them. Therefore, they had to keep each of the activities dynamic and needed to move onto the next activity fairly quickly to keep people interested and engaged. However,

they heard from many of the parents who took part in these workshops that they really enjoyed being part of this process and having time to think about their children's diets, and more broadly about the food environment.

Specific reflections on implementing the workshop with stakeholders

In the professional stakeholder group it was mentioned that participants were very happy to get to know each other's way of working, and they were genuinely impressed by the work that everyone does.

Annex

Food literacy		Leuven	Oxfordshire
	Drivers and barriers scientific literature	<i>Qualities (+) Bottlenecks (-)</i>	<i>Qualities (+) Bottlenecks (-)</i>
Micro	Knowledge	Knowledge (-)	Knowledge (-) Involving kids/ passing on knowledge (+)
	Skills	Skills (-) Cooking together with children (+)	Skills (-)
	Facilities		
	Awareness and values	Awareness and change of routines in purchases (-)	Trying to avoid plastic (+)
	Attitude and beliefs	Disinterest (-)	Attitude for not wasting food (+)
	Information		Information and lots of recipes available (+)
Meso	Advertising		Prevalence of advertising (-)
	Food education in schools		

	Community cooking and eating initiatives	Initiatives promoting healthy eating, Tournee Minerale, Veggie Challenge (+)	
Macro	Food policy and regulations		
	Nutritional education programs	Farm education programs/ Farmer & companies (+)	
	Campaings		
	Sustainability strategies		
	Marketing/ promotion	Branded promotions like McDonald's (-) Positive promotion of plant-based diets (+) Celebrities who cook healthy (+)	
	Social and cultural norms		
Food preferences		Leuven	Oxfordshire
	Drivers and barriers scientific literature	<i>Qualities (+) Bottlenecks (-)</i>	<i>Qualities (+) Bottlenecks (-)</i>
	Taste		
	Appeal and sensory preferences		
	Health status, perceptions and behaviours		Modelling good behaviour/ eating with the kids (+)

Micro			
	Convenience		Convenience with (fast) food (-)
	Experiences, habits and routines		Kids want to eat 'now' (-) Background and experience (+)
	Attitudes		
	Values and social identity		
	Family influence	Limited preferences child (-)	Diet of partners (-) Limited preferences children/ fussy toddlers (-)
Meso	Cultural food practices		
	Social influences	Influence social environment (-)	
	Social support/ networks		
Macro	Social, cultural norms		The 'more is better' attitude (-)
	Eating culture	Tradition and eating culture (like meat)(-)	

	Environmental and ethical trends		
	Food marketing and (social) media		

Food availability		Leuven	Oxfordshire
	Drivers and barriers scientific literature	<i>Qualities (+)</i> <i>Bottlenecks (-)</i>	<i>Qualities (+) Bottlenecks (-)</i>
Micro	Personal resources (time and transport options)	Time availability daily life (shopping/ cooking) (-)	Limited time for cooking (-)
	Availability of H&S food household	Water as standard drink (+)	
Meso	Availability of H&S food schools, workplaces, hospitals and other institutions	Low availability H&S food school (-) Warm meals at school (+) School treats abolished (+) More attention to vegetarian and vegan options (+) More availability of frozen vegetables and fruits (+) Healthy drinks at school (+)	Availability of fruit and veg all year round (not seasonal/local) (-)

		Free fruit at school (+)	
	Availability of H&S food (supermarkets, farmers' markets, grocery stores, restaurants) close to home	<p>Rise of fast food chains (-)</p> <p>No specific shop for specific food (-)</p> <p>Low availability H&S food supermarket and budget-friendly supermarkets (-)</p> <p>Low availability H&S food take-away</p> <p>Influence daily physical environment (-)</p> <p>Healthier fast food chains, vegetarian snack bars (+)</p> <p>More vegetarian options in restaurants (+)</p> <p>Healthy children's menu (+)</p> <p>Recreational facilities offering healthy meals for children (+)</p>	<p>Lack of choice of shops (-)</p> <p>Supermarkets open and nearby (+)</p>
	Availability of culturally appropriate foods or foods that meet specific dietary needs		
	Food distribution systems within the community		
	Availability social programs like food banks		
	Urban agriculture like community gardens		<p>No allotment/space for growing own food (-)</p> <p>Access to a growing space (+)</p>
	Availability of H&S food online	Services like 'Hello Fresh' (+)	

Macro	Food policy and regulation (influence food availability, import/export regulations, food security policies)	Almost no restrictions sale unhealthy food (-)	
	Agricultural systems		
	Environmental policies		
	Food production		

Food affordability		Leuven	Oxfordshire
	Drivers and barriers scientific literature	Qualities (+) Bottlenecks (-)	Qualities (+) Bottlenecks (-)
Micro	Financial capacity	Income (-)	
	Food prices	Food prices (-)	Price of F&V/recipe boxes (-)
	Financial support		No F&V rewards (in apps) (-)
Meso	Local community access like food banks, food programs and community gardens	Accessibility unhealthy food (-) Relative costs: H&S foods (-)	No funding for high quality of school food (-)

		<p>Free fruit at school (+)</p> <p>Discounts on healthy food items (+)</p> <p>Initiatives like self-harvest/ vegetable gardens (+)</p>	<p>Free school meals (+)</p> <p>Food bank, vouchers,</p> <p>Community larder (+)</p>
Macro	National policies on subsidies, food aid, food price regulation etc.		Value of F&V (true cost of production)(-)